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NGI Explorers Program

Deliverable 1.4

Beneficiaries dataset

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Abstract

This deliverable reports on public Open Dataset containing the list of beneficiaries and project description.

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The NGI Explorers Consortium is the following:

Participant number	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
01	F6S Network Limited	F6S	UK
02	Australo Interinnov Marketing Lab S.L.	AUS	ES
03	Zabala Innovation Consulting S.A.	ZAB	ES

EXPLANATION ON DELIVERABLE

The list of Beneficiaries including their project description, Grantee, matched US Node, direct contact to Explorer via social media, and a link to a public video describing the EU-US collaboration is published on the project [website](#). Beneficiaries per each Open Call are listed in dedicated bookmark “Meet the Explorers”:

- [Mission #1](#)
- [Mission #2](#)
- [Mission #3](#)

Funding:

With concern to the fund received, this information was reported in D1.5 Progress report. Given the pandemic situation and several amendments done to the subgrantee agreement, which were reported in the Periodic Report and D1.5, the final update of the grant per each Explorer will be added to the website once all expeditions are finalised. Currently most Explorers have status of hybrid expedition (partially completed remotely in Europe and in the US) attempting to travel to the US for at least one or two months, given recent approval of their visa’s applications. Their grant can be still a subject of recalculation depends on the final execution per expedition.

A sample of description on the website.